

1 **Boosting biogas valorisation via bioconversion**
2 **into the high profit margin product, ectoine.**

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20 **Abstract**

21 This study constitutes the first proof of concept of biogas bioconversion into the high profit
22 margin product ectoine (1000 \$ kg⁻¹). Two haloalkaliphilic methanotrophic inocula were
23 tested, the pure strain *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z and an enriched methanotrophic
24 consortium. First, the production of ectoine from biogas was assessed in batch bioreactors. The
25 presence of CO₂ and H₂S did not exert a negative effect on the growth of either inoculum, and
26 ectoine yields up to 49 mg ectoine g biomass⁻¹ were obtained. A second experiment conducted
27 in bioreactors confirmed the feasibility of the process under continuous mode (with ectoine
28 yields of 109 mg g biomass⁻¹). Finally, this study revealed that high dilution rates (i.e. 0.5 day⁻¹)
29 and process operation with a consortium composed of methylotrophic/non-methylotrophic
30 ectoine producers enhanced biogas bioconversion. This research reveals the basis for the
31 application of this innovative technology and could boost the economic performance of
32 anaerobic digestion.

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43 1. Introduction

44 The anaerobic digestion of organic solid waste and high-strength wastewaters results in a
45 cost-effective recovery of their chemical energy and carbon in the form of biogas.
46 Unfortunately, logistical constraints in biogas utilization often means that it is flared or vented
47 to the atmosphere in low-medium size facilities, thereby contributing to greenhouse gas
48 emissions (Yang et al., 2014). These constraints include co-occurrence of contaminants (CO₂,
49 H₂S, methyl siloxanes and halocarbons), high investment costs required for on-site energy
50 recovery, and technical/regulatory limitations for the transportation and storage of biogas.
51 These limitations have encouraged increased research on novel biotechnological strategies for
52 biogas valorisation such as the bioconversion of biogas into high added value
53 products(Chistoserdova and Kalyuzhnaya, 2018; Pieja et al., 2017).

54 The use of biogas as a substrate for the production of methanol (Duan et al., 2011; Sheets et
55 al., 2016) and bioplastics (Pieja et al., 2016) has been recently explored in literature. However,
56 the bioconversion of biogas into ectoine, probably one of the most profitable microbial
57 products, has never been addressed. Ectoine currently retails in the industry at approximately
58 US\$1000 kg⁻¹ and its demand increases every year (global consumption of 15000 t y⁻¹)(Strong
59 et al., 2016). This compatible solute is synthesized by bacteria to survive in salt-rich
60 environments because it is an effective stabilizer for enzymes, DNA-protein complexes and
61 nucleic acids, making it an attractive compound for the pharmaceutical and medical
62 industry(Czech et al., 2018). Recent studies have demonstrated that methanotrophs are able to
63 produce ectoine from diluted CH₄ emissions under continuous and discontinuous growth
64 modes using different bioreactor configurations(Cantera et al., 2018a). For instance, the
65 methanotrophic haloalkaliphilic bacterium *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum*(Khmelenina et al.,

66 1997) is able to accumulate intra-cellular ectoine concentrations of up to 75 mg g biomass⁻¹
67 during the treatment of dilute methane emissions under continuous operation(Cantera et al.,
68 2017b, 2016). Additionally, a recent study identified a methanotrophic consortia able to
69 produce ectoine up to 95 mg g biomass⁻¹ using dilute methane as the only feedstock(Cantera et
70 al., 2018b). Unfortunately, the ectoine production reported using methanotrophs are far below
71 those typically obtained using sugars as feedstock and *Halomonas elongata* as ectoine
72 synthesizing organisms. In this context, CH₄ bioconversion into ectoine is typically limited by
73 the low solubility of methane in the aqueous phase, which hinders process operation at high
74 cell densities and therefore limits ectoine production rates(Cantera et al., 2017a, 2016). The
75 use of biogas as a renewable source of methane (typically containing 55-70 % CH₄) can
76 increase CH₄ availability to the microbial community as a result of the superior gas-liquid
77 concentration gradient, which could ultimately enhance bacterial growth and ectoine
78 productivity. In addition, the use of suspended growth bubble column reactors with internal
79 gas recirculation have been recently shown to support high CH₄ mass transfer rates and high
80 cell densities(Estrada et al., 2014).

81 This study assessed the potential of biogas valorization into ectoine under batch and
82 continuous mode using both a pure strain of *M. alcaliphilum* 20Z and a CH₄ enriched
83 haloalkaliphilic consortium with special emphasis on the role of CO₂ and H₂S. The influence
84 of the presence of CO₂ and the dilution rate on the performance of bubble column bioreactors
85 with internal gas recirculation to support higher ectoine productivities was also evaluated.

86

87 **2. Materials and methods**

88 *2.1. Chemicals and mineral salt medium*

89 The mineral salt medium (MSM) used for the cultivation of the haloalkaliphilic
90 methanotrophs was a high pH (9.0) and high-salt content (6 % NaCl) medium prepared
91 according to Kalyuhnaya et al. 2008 (Kalyuzhnaya et al., 2008). All chemicals and reagents
92 were purchased from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain) with a purity higher than 99.0 %. CH₄ (purity
93 ≥ 99.5), O₂ (purity $\geq 99\%$), CO₂ (purity > 99.9) and He (purity $\geq 95\%$) were purchased from
94 Abello Linde (Spain).

95 2.2. Microorganisms and inocula preparation

96 The experiments were carried out using a pure strain of *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum* 20Z
97 (*M. alcaliphilum*) and a CH₄ enriched haloalkaliphilic consortium. The inocula were grown for
98 30 days at 25 °C in 120 mL sterile glass bottles containing 40 mL of MSM and incubated at
99 200 rpm in an orbital shaker prior to batch and continuous biogas bioconversion experiments.
100 Inoculum bottles were closed with gas-tight butyl septa and aluminum caps, and 50 % (v/v) of
101 the air headspace was replaced by CH₄.

102 *M. alcaliphilum* was purchased from DSMZ (Leibniz Institute, German Collection of
103 Microorganisms and Cell Cultures). The enriched haloalkaliphilic consortium initially
104 consisted of: *Methylobacterium* (44.2 %), *Methylophaga* (22.5 %), *Gelidibacter* (11.5 %),
105 *Marinobacter* (9.1 %), *Halomonas* (4.9 %), *Oceanibaculum* (2.8 %), *Bacillus* (3.7 %) and
106 *Yeosuana* (2.1 %)(Cantera et al., 2018b). This consortium was enriched from fresh activated
107 sludge of a denitrification-nitrification wastewater treatment plant with seawater intrusion
108 (Cantabria, Spain) mixed with cow manure and soil. The community analysis of the
109 haloalkaliphilic consortium was carried out by sequencing two variable 16S rRNA gene
110 regions, V4 and V5, in three separate sequencing runs on Illumina's HiSeq2000 platform using
111 the 515f/926r primer pair according to Cantera et al. 2018(Cantera et al., 2018b).

112 2.3. Batch biogas bioconversion into ectoine

113 The influence of CO₂, H₂S, and of microbial inoculum on CH₄ bioconversion into ectoine
114 was assessed in duplicate batch-wise in gas-tight bioreactors (Table A₁, supporting
115 information). Gas tight bottles of 2.1 L were filled with 400 mL of MSM, closed with butyl-
116 rubber stoppers and aluminum crimp seals and inoculated to a final biomass concentration of
117 40 ± 10 mg TSS L⁻¹ (Table A₁, supporting information) by adding 20 mL of the corresponding
118 fresh inoculum. The batch experiments were performed under three different O₂-supplemented
119 headspace atmospheres in duplicate (v/v): H₂S-free biogas (CH₄:O₂:CO₂:He at
120 31.5:55.0:13.27:0.23 %), biogas (CH₄:O₂:CO₂:H₂S at 31.5:55.0:13.27:0.23 %) and pure
121 methane (CH₄:O₂:He at 31.5:55.0:13.5 %) until complete methane depletion. Three controls
122 without biomass were also conducted under the same conditions (Table A₁; TS7, 8 and 9) to
123 rule out the occurrence of abiotic CH₄ removal. The headspace mixtures were prepared in 25
124 L-Tedlar bags (Sigma-Aldrich®, St. Louis, USA) according to López et al., 2018(López et al.,
125 2018). The systems were incubated at 25 ± 0.5 °C in a temperature-controlled room and stirred
126 magnetically at 300 rpm for a total of 18 ± 2 days. The headspace concentration of CH₄, CO₂,
127 O₂ and H₂S was periodically measured by GC-TCD. Liquid samples (10 mL) were periodically
128 drawn to monitor the concentration of total suspended solids (TSS) and ectoine. The pH of the
129 cultivation broth was measured at the beginning and at the end of each test series.

130 2.4. Continuous biogas bioconversion into ectoine

131 The experimental set-up consisted of a cylindrical glass bubble column bioreactor (BCB) (0.08
132 m internal diameter × 0.4 m height) with 2 L of working volume (Afora S.A., Spain) (Figure
133 1). This bioreactor was fed with H₂S-free biogas similar to the one produced in waste treatment
134 plants after biogas upgrading. The BCB was operated with *Methylobacterium alcaliphilum*

135 during 2 different operational stages, stages S1 and S2, and with the haloalkaliphilic
136 consortium during 4 different operational stages, stages S3, S4, S5 and S6. A gas stream of 60
137 mL min⁻¹ containing 35% (v/v) of CH₄ (corresponding to a CH₄ loading rate of 358.5 ± 62.7 g
138 m⁻³ h⁻¹), 10% (v/v) of CO₂ and 55% (v/v) of O₂ was fed to the system using mass flow
139 controllers (Aalborg™, USA) and three ultra-fine bubble diffusers located at the bottom of
140 the BCB. This resulted in an empty bed residence time (EBRT) of 33.3 min. CO₂ was replaced
141 by He to assess the influence of CO₂ on process performance during stages 5 and 6. An internal
142 gas recirculation of 1 L min⁻¹ (corresponding to an internal gas-recycling ratio Q_R/Q = 16.67)
143 was implemented in the BCB during stages S1, S3, S5 and S6 (Table 1).

144 <Figure 1>

145 The recirculation stream was cooled down in a 1 L jacketed condenser maintained at 20 °C.
146 An aliquot of 100 mL of cultivation broth was daily replaced with fresh sterile MSM during
147 stages S1, S2, S3, S4 and S5. During S6, the MSM exchange rate was increased to 1 L d⁻¹ in
148 order to elucidate the potential for microbial community inhibition by secondary metabolites.
149 In that case, 900 mL of cultivation broth were centrifuged for 10 min at 10000 rpm and the
150 pellet was re-suspended in 1000 mL of fresh MSM and returned to the BCB. In both cases,
151 100 mL of cultivation broth were used to measure the pH, total suspended solids (TSS), total
152 organic carbon (TOC), inorganic carbon (IC) and ectoine accumulation in the biomass. The
153 operational conditions in each stage were maintained for 30 days, which ensured process
154 operation under steady state conditions. An abiotic test with MSM was initially performed for
155 5 days at the above described operational conditions to assess any potential removal of CH₄ by
156 adsorption or photodegradation in the experimental set-up. CO₂ and CH₄ gas concentrations in
157 the BCB inlet and outlet streams and the pressure at the inlet stream were daily measured.

158

<Table 1>

159 The elucidation of the limiting step in the biogas bioconversion process (gas-liquid mass
160 transfer or microbial activity) was carried out by injecting 5 mL of cultivation broth into a 15
161 mL vial closed with a butyl septum in quintuplicate, sealed with an aluminum cap and
162 supplemented with 0.1 mL of H₂SO₄ to stop biological activity. The vial was immediately
163 shaken vigorously and allowed to equilibrate for 2 h at 25 °C prior to the determination of the
164 CH₄ headspace concentration(Frutos et al., 2014). The CH₄ concentration in the cultivation
165 broth was then calculated using the individual gas and liquid volumes and the Henry's law
166 constant for CH₄ (30 at 25 °C)(Sander, 2015). If the process was limited by the mass transfer
167 of CH₄ to the community, the concentration of CH₄ in the liquid phase would be zero since all
168 CH₄ transferred would have been degraded by the microbial community. If the microbial
169 activity was rate limiting, the CH₄ concentration in the cultivation broth would correspond to
170 that in equilibrium with the outlet gas stream(Frutos et al., 2014).

171 *2.5. Analytical procedures*

172 CO₂ and CH₄ gas concentrations were determined in a Bruker 430 gas chromatograph (Palo
173 Alto, USA) coupled with a thermal conductivity detector and equipped with a CP-Molsieve
174 5A (15 m × 0.53 μm × 15 μm) and a P-PoraBOND Q (25 m × 0.53 μm × 10 μm) columns.
175 Oven, detector and injector temperatures were maintained constant at 45, 200 and 150 °C for
176 5 min, respectively. The pressure in the inlet stream was measured using a differential pressure
177 sensor IFM (Essen, Germany). The pH in the cultivation broth was analyzed using a glass
178 membrane electrode PH BASIC 20, Crison (Barcelona, Spain). The TSS concentration was
179 determined according to standard methods ([American Water Works Association, 2012](#)). TOC

180 and IC concentrations were measured following sample filtration (0.45 μm) using a TOC-
181 VCSH analyzer (Shimadzu, Japan).

182 The intra-cellular ectoine concentration was determined using 2 mL of cultivation broth
183 centrifuged at 9000 $\times g$ and 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 min. Then, 2 mL of ethanol at 50 % and 25 \pm 5 mg of
184 0.1-mm-diameter zirconia/silica beads (BioSpec, Spain) were added to the Eppendorf tube
185 containing the pellet (modified from Cantera et al. (2016)) (Cantera et al., 2016). Microbial
186 cells were then disrupted using a Mini-BeadBeater-16 (BioSpec, Spain) at 1048 $\times g$ for 1 min
187 and the suspension was kept overnight at room temperature. The supernatant of the suspensions
188 was employed for ectoine analysis prior centrifugation at 9000 $\times g$ and 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 15 min followed
189 by filtration through 0.22 μm filters (Filter-lab, Barcelona). The intra-cellular ectoine
190 concentration (mg ectoine g biomass $^{-1}$) was calculated using the TSS concentration (g L $^{-1}$) of
191 the corresponding cultivation broth. The concentration of ectoine was measured by HPLC-UV
192 in a 717 plus auto-sampler (Waters, Bellefonte, USA) coupled with a UV Dual λ Absorbance
193 detector (Waters, Bellefonte, USA) at 220 nm and 40 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using a LC-18 AQ μ C Supelcosil
194 column (Sigma Aldrich, Spain) and a C18 AQ + pre-column (Sigma Aldrich, Spain). A
195 phosphate buffer, consisting of 0.8 mM K₂HPO₄ \cdot 3H₂O and 6.0 mM Na₂HPO₄ \cdot 12H₂O, was
196 used as a mobile phase at 25 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and a flow rate of 1 mL min $^{-1}$ (Cantera et al., 2016; Tanimura
197 et al., 2013). Ectoine quantification was carried out using external standards of commercially
198 available ectoine ((S)-b-2-methyl-1,4,5,6-tetrahydro pyrimidine-4-carboxylic acid, purity
199 95%, Sigma Aldrich, Spain). The ectoine retention time ranged from 2.32 to 2.35 min
200 depending on the column pressure. The detection and quantification limits (DL and QL,
201 respectively) were calculated via determination of the signal-to-noise ratio. In this sense, a
202 signal-to-noise ratio of 2:1 is considered acceptable for estimating the detection limit, while a

203 signal-to-noise ratio of 10:1 is necessary to determine the quantification limit (ICH Expert
204 working Group, 2005). The DL and QL of ectoine in the MSM used were 0.4 mg L⁻¹ and 0.65
205 mg L⁻¹, respectively.

206 *2.6. Data analysis*

207 The statistical data analysis was performed using SPSS 20.0 (IBM, USA). The results are
208 given as the average ± standard deviation. The homogeneity of the variance of the parameters
209 was evaluated using a Levene test followed by an ANOVA and post-hoc analysis (Tukey and
210 Bonferroni). Differences were considered to be significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

211 *2.7. Bacterial community analysis*

212 Aliquots of 5 mL of the cultivation broth of the BCB from stages S3, S4, S5 and S6 were
213 centrifuged at 9000 ×g for 10 min (Table 1). The resting pellet was used for DNA extraction
214 using the FastDNA SPIN Kit for Soil (MP Biomedicals, Solon, OH) according to the
215 manufacturer's instructions. DNA was quantified with a Nanodrop spectrophotometer
216 (Nanodrop Technologies, Wilmington, DE). Extracted DNA was arrayed in 96 well plate
217 format and each plate contained extra pure PCR water as negative control and a mock
218 community as positive control (ZymoBIOMICS™ Microbial Community DNA Standard, CA,
219 USA). The V4-V5 region of the 16S rRNA gene was PCR amplified following the instructions
220 by Kozich et al. (2013)(Kozich et al., 2013). PCR was performed using a Peltier Thermal
221 Cycler PTC-200 (MJResearch) with an initial denaturation at 95 °C for 2 min; followed by 30
222 cycles of denaturation at 95 °C for 20 s, annealing at 55 °C for 15 s and extension at 72 °C for
223 10 min. PCR products were cleaned up and normalized using the SequalPrep Normalization
224 Plate Kit (Thermofisher scientific, USA). After normalization, 5 µl of each well were pooled
225 to give a single library containing all the samples and controls. The library was spiked with

226 10% PhiX (Illumina) and sequenced on an Illumina MiSeq instrument. The 16S rRNA gene
227 sequences were processed using Mothur v1.40.5 following the Mother SOP
228 (https://www.mothur.org/wiki/MiSeq_SOP(Schloss et al., 2009)). Quality filtered sequences
229 were aligned to the Silva 16S rRNA gene reference database(Quast et al., 2013; Yilmaz et al.,
230 2014), preclustered by abundance, with chimeric sequences being removed according to
231 Phandanouvong-Lozano et al., 2018 (Phandanouvong-Lozano et al., 2018). Sequences were
232 then classified and annotated into Operational Taxonomic Units (OTUs) using the Ribosomal
233 Database Project (RDP) with 100 bootstrap iterations and 80% confidence cutoff(Cole et al.,
234 2014). The plots were generated with R version 3.5.1 and RStudio 1.1.442, and the gplot
235 package 3.0.1 and the package tax4fun for R was used to build the heatmap (R Core Team,
236 2018) The nucleotide sequence dataset obtained in this study can be accessed from the NCBI
237 Sequence Read Archive as bioproject SRR8602910
238 (<https://trace.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Traces/sra/?run=SRR8602910>).

239

240 **3. Results and Discussion**

241 3.1. Batch biogas bioconversion into ectoine

242 This experiment demonstrated the viability of biogas bioconversion into ectoine by *M.*
243 *alcaliphilum* and by the enriched haloalkaliphilic consortium batchwise. A total of 6 batch tests
244 series (TS) were conducted in duplicate (table A₁, supporting information) with *M.*
245 *alcaliphilum* under atmospheres containing methane (TS1), H₂S-free biogas (TS2) and biogas
246 (TS3), and with the haloalkaliphilic consortium under atmospheres containing methane (TS4),
247 H₂S-free biogas (TS5) and biogas (TS6). The presence of CO₂ and H₂S did not have a negative
248 effect on the growth of the microorganisms tested at a P<0.05. Additionally, CH₄ degradation

249 and CO₂ production from biogas and a H₂S-free biogas atmospheres were comparable to those
250 with CH₄ regardless of the inoculum (Figure 2). The pH decreased from 9 ± 0.1 to 8.4 ± 0.2 in
251 the *M. alcaliphilum* tests, but remained constant during the cultivation of the haloalkaliphilic
252 consortium (final pH of 8.7 ± 0.3). The volumetric *M. alcaliphilum* growth rates were 0.020 ±
253 0.001, 0.019 ± 0.002 and 0.021 ± 0.001 mg L⁻¹ h⁻¹ in TS1, TS2 and TS3, respectively, which
254 were not significantly different (P<0.05) than the rates recorded for the haloalkaliphilic
255 consortium (0.018 ± 0.005, 0.017 ± 0.004, 0.019 ± 0.001 mg L⁻¹ h⁻¹ in TS4, TS5 and TS6,
256 respectively).

257 <Figure 2>

258 Similarly, no significant effect of the gas headspace composition was observed on the
259 production of ectoine. The accumulation of ectoine in *M. alcaliphilum* was 28.9 ± 3.7 mg g
260 biomass⁻¹ when provided with CH₄, but 25.8 ± 1.1 and 25.9 ± 0.9 mg g biomass⁻¹ under
261 atmospheres of H₂S-free biogas and biogas, respectively. On the other hand, the
262 haloalkaliphilic consortium was able to accumulate significantly higher (P<0.05) intra-cellular
263 ectoine concentrations than *M. alcaliphilum* regardless of the headspace gas composition (46.8
264 ± 2.5, 42.5 ± 5, and 45.2 ± 2.4 mg g biomass⁻¹ in CH₄, biogas, and H₂S-free biogas respectively)
265 (Figure 3).

266 <Figure 3>

267 This presence of high concentrations of CH₄ (31.5 %) likely led to increased intra-cellular
268 ectoine concentrations in *M. alcaliphilum* and the bacterial consortium due to an increase in
269 substrate availability as previously reported by Cantera et al. 2016 (Cantera et al., 2016).

270 *3.2 Continuous biogas bioconversion into ectoine*

271 Six operational stages were implemented to assess the continuous bioconversion of CH₄
272 from biogas into ectoine in a BCB with and without gas recirculation (Table 1). The first and
273 second stages were conducted using upgraded biogas (70 % CH₄, 30 % CO₂) as a feedstock
274 and *M. alcaliphilum* as inoculum. Stage 1, operated at 1 L min⁻¹ of internal gas recirculation,
275 resulted in average ectoine contents of 2.9 ± 0.4 mg g biomass⁻¹ and methane elimination
276 capacities (ECs) of 6.1 ± 0.7 g m⁻³ h⁻¹, respectively (Figure 4). Operating the bioreactor with
277 internal gas recirculation allowed decoupling the K_{LaG/A} from the gas residence time and
278 therefore increasing the CH₄ mass transfer as a result of the higher turbulence in the cultivation
279 broth. However, CH₄ bioconversion into ectoine was not efficient due to the difficulties *M.*
280 *alcaliphilum* had in growing under the conditions tested (TSS = 0.4 ± 0.02 g L⁻¹). This
281 bacterium is known to be sensitive to mechanical stress(Cantera et al., 2017a), thus mechanical
282 cell disruption induced by the internal gas recirculation likely accounted for the low
283 bioconversion rates. Surprisingly, however, process operation without internal gas
284 recirculation during S2 did not significantly enhance bioreactor performance. The absence of
285 recirculation resulted in ectoine production of 4.0 ± 0.6 mg g biomass⁻¹, biomass concentration
286 of 0.4 ± 0.05 g L⁻¹, and an EC of 7.7 ± 0.6 g m⁻³ h⁻¹(Figure 4). Thus, process performance was
287 very low compared to previous experiments conducted with *M. alcaliphilum* (Cantera et al.,
288 2017b; Khmelenina et al., 1997) at high CH₄ concentrations, which are known to significantly
289 improve the synthesis of ectoine (Akberdin et al., 2018; But et al., 2013; Cantera et al., 2016).
290 The results of the mass transfer limitation tests in S1 and S2 suggested that process operation
291 was limited by biological activity. The average CH₄ concentration in the aqueous phase was
292 7.3 ± 0.5 g m⁻³, corresponding to the concentration in equilibrium with the CH₄ in the gas phase
293 (215. 8 ± 0.6 g m⁻³)(Cantera et al., 2015).

294 The low performance of *M. alcaliphilum* was attributed to the low pH prevailing in the
295 cultivation broth during S1 and S2 (7.6 ± 0.2), since *M. alcaliphilum* is an alkalophile organism
296 that grows at an optimum pH of 9(Kalyuzhnaya et al., 2008). Although the pH of the MSM
297 used was 9 and had a strong buffer capacity (by addition of 5 mM carbonate/50 mM
298 bicarbonate), the continuous supplementation of CO₂ in the gas phase likely caused a pH drop
299 that partially inhibited *M. alcaliphilum* growth.

300 <Figure 4>

301 In contrast, operation with a mixed bacterial haloalkaliphilic consortium under conditions to
302 similar S1 and S2, resulted in higher biomass concentrations (0.8 ± 0.03 g L⁻¹ in S3 and $0.8 \pm$
303 0.02 g L⁻¹ in S4) and higher ectoine production (24.0 ± 2.1 and 25.0 ± 1.2 mg g biomass⁻¹ in
304 S3 and S4, respectively). Despite the higher ectoine production, the consortium's ECs in S3
305 and S4 were not significantly different than those of *M. alcaliphilum* under the same
306 operational conditions. Interestingly, the pH of the cultivation broth in S3 and S4 remained
307 relatively constant at 8.5 ± 0.3 , possibly due to the production of basic extracellular metabolites
308 that buffered most of the CO₂-mediated decrease in pH, as reported for a wide range of marine
309 bacteria(De Carvalho and Fernandes, 2010). However, the CH₄ concentration in the aqueous
310 phase was 5.1 ± 0.4 g m⁻³, corresponding to the equilibrium concentration with the CH₄
311 concentration in the gas phase (180 ± 14 g m⁻³)(Cantera et al., 2015), which indicated that the
312 system was limited by microbial activity.

313 CO₂ was replaced by He in the gas phase during S5 in order to elucidate the role of CO₂
314 during biogas conversion with the haloalkaliphilic consortium(Martin et al., 2003). However,
315 the ectoine concentration recorded in S5 was 19.9 ± 2.3 mg g biomass⁻¹, statistically similar to
316 that achieved in S3 and S4. The EC (8.9 ± 0.7 g m⁻³ h⁻¹) in S5 was also low and statistically

317 similar to those recorded in the previous stages. Although biomass concentration increased to
318 $1.5 \pm 0.03 \text{ g L}^{-1}$, biogas bioconversion was limited by biological activity in S5, as shown by the
319 CH_4 concentration measured in the cultivation broth ($6.7 \pm 0.3 \text{ g m}^{-3}$).

320 Given that the pH of the cultivation broth in S5 was 8.8 ± 0.05 , which suggested that the
321 poor CH_4 biodegradation performance could be caused by the accumulation of inhibitory
322 metabolites. Such a mechanism was consistent with the observation that the TOC concentration
323 of the cultivation broth in S5 ($485 \pm 20.1 \text{ mg C L}^{-1}$) was, significantly higher than the TOC
324 concentrations previously reported as cell growth inhibitory by other authors (above 100 mg
325 C L^{-1}) (Estrada et al., 2014; Mancebo Uriel et al., 2014). Therefore, a new MSM dilution rate
326 of 0.5 day^{-1} was implemented during S6 in order to maintain TOC concentrations below 100
327 mg C L^{-1} (average value of $\sim 91.5 \pm 4.1 \text{ mg C L}^{-1}$ during S6). This new dilution rate resulted in
328 a gradual increase in the EC to steady state values of $18.2 \pm 1.3 \text{ g m}^{-3} \text{ h}^{-1}$ concomitantly with
329 an enhanced synthesis of ectoine up to $108.7 \pm 4.8 \text{ mg biomass}^{-1}$ and an increase in biomass
330 concentrations up to $1.9 \pm 0.02 \text{ g L}^{-1}$ (Figure A1, supporting information). The mass transfer
331 limitation test conducted during S6 demonstrated that the bioreactor was no longer limited by
332 microbial activity. The ectoine yield for S6 was similar to typical yields ($75\text{-}94 \text{ mg g biomass}^{-1}$)
333 reported for continuous bioreactors operated with haloalkaliphilic methanotrophs treating
334 dilute CH_4 emissions (Cantera et al., 2017b; Cantera et al., 2018b), but not as high as expected
335 given the higher CH_4 concentrations used here. This was likely due to the stationary growth of
336 the culture in the pulsed batch format of S6. The correlation between ectoine production and
337 exponential growth has been consistently observed under batch and continuous
338 cultivations (Cantera et al., 2017a, 2016; Khmelenina et al., 1997).

339 3.3 Microbial population diversity and community profile during continuous biogas
340 bioconversion into ectoine

341 Process operation during S1 and S2 was conducted with a pure culture of *M. alcaliphilum*
342 20Z purchased from DSMZ and therefore the microbial community was not analysed during
343 those stages. The BCB was inoculated in S3 with an haloalkaliphilic consortium previously
344 shown to contain 7 main genera: *Methylomicrobium* (44.2 %), *Methylophaga* (22.5 %),
345 *Gelidibacter* (11.5 %), *Marinobacter* (9.1 %), *Halomonas* (4.9 %), *Oceanibaculum* (2.8 %),
346 *Bacillus* (3.7 %) and *Yeosuana* (2.1 %)(Cantera et al., 2018b). At the end of S3, the genera
347 *Methylophaga* (33.2 %) and *Methylomicrobium* (22.2 %) were still the most abundant, while
348 other important ectoine producers such as members of the genus *Halomonas* (9.6 %) and
349 *Marinobacter* (5.9 %) were also present in the cultivation broth(Czech et al., 2018; Pastor et
350 al., 2010). The genus *Nitratireductor* (9.5 %) also exhibited a high relative abundance, likely
351 due to the high concentration of nitrate of the MSM (Figure 5). This genus is able to produce
352 ectoine and grow in marine environments using nitrate as electron acceptor and some sugars
353 and aminoacids as carbon and electron sources(Singh et al., 2012). Additionally, the genus
354 *Xanthomonas* was also present in S3 (5 %). Many *Xanthomonas* produce exopolysaccharides,
355 which could have played a role in pH buffering.

356 <Figure 5>

357 The elimination of gas recirculation during S4 did not impact the population structure of the
358 BCB and only influenced the main genera relative abundance: *Methylophaga* (27.6 %),
359 *Methylomicrobium* (19.3 %), *Marinobacter* (7.1 %), *Halomonas* (11.7 %), *Nitratireductor*
360 (11.2 %) and *Xanthomonas* (5.3 %). However, the change in the carbon feedstock during S5
361 from H₂S- free biogas to CH₄ mediated a shift in the bacterial population structure, with

362 *Methylobacterium* as the main genus (39.4 %) followed by *Methylophaga* (22.4 %) and a
363 significant decrease in the share of *Halomonas* and *Marinobacter* (1.4 and 0.4 % of the total
364 bacterial population, respectively). Both *Halomonas* and *Marinobacter* are marine bacteria and
365 their optimal growth is in the majority of species in a pH range from 7.5 to 8.5 (Das and
366 Mangwani, 2015; Mata et al., 2002). In this context, the increase in the pH to 9.0 mediated by
367 the lower CO₂ concentrations in the inlet gas stream, could have caused this microbial
368 population shift to species that are characteristic of soda lakes with higher pHs
369 (*Methylobacterium* and *Methylophaga*) (Sorokin et al., 2014).

370 The increase in the MSM exchange rate during S6 likely washed out the inhibitory
371 metabolites such as nitrite or secondary metabolites from methane oxidation (Nyerges et al.,
372 2010; Roco et al., 2016) that accumulated in the BCB at lower dilution rates. This was
373 accompanied by an increase in the relative abundance of *Methylobacterium* (22.9 %) and
374 *Methylophaga* (41.7 %), an improved EC, higher biomass production, and better ectoine yield
375 (Figure A₂, supporting information).

376 Finally, it should be stressed the fact that the ectoine yields obtained were not as high as
377 those expected based on previous studies (Cantera et al., 2018b). These low ectoine yields were
378 probably related to the shift in the bacterial population when H₂S-free biogas was replaced by
379 pure CH₄, since the genera *Marinobacter* and *Halomonas* have been previously described as
380 more efficient ectoine producers (De Carvalho and Fernandes, 2010; Pastor et al., 2010) and
381 *Methylophaga* and *Methylobacterium* are methanol and methane oxidizers. In this regard,
382 biogas might be more efficiently transformed into ectoine by a bespoke consortium of
383 *Halomonas* or *Marinobacter* and *Methylophaga* or *Methylobacterium* using upgraded biogas
384 (H₂S-free biogas).

385

386 **4. Conclusions**

387 This inter-disciplinary research constitutes the first proof of concept for the production of
388 ectoine from biogas and provides the first insights into the operational conditions needed to
389 achieve high ectoine production rates. Indeed, the dilution rates should be optimized to prevent
390 the accumulation of toxic metabolites that partially inhibit biomass growth, CH₄ abatement
391 and ectoine synthesis.

392 Moreover, the most suitable bacterial consortium to make the process profitable thus, biogas
393 might be more efficiently transformed into ectoine by a bespoke consortium of haloalkaliphilic
394 methanotrophs, methylotrophs and heterotrophs, such as *Halomonas* or *Marinobacter* and
395 *Methylophaga* or *Methylomicrobium*.

396 Indeed, this study reveals the basis for the true application of this innovative technology
397 based on the transformation of the second most important GHG into the most expensive
398 product generated by microorganisms and will boost the development of a new generation of
399 biogas upgrading technologies based on extremophile methanotrophs capable of creating
400 substantial value from methane mitigation.

401

402 **ABBREVIATIONS**

403 MSM, Mineral Salt Medium, BCB, Bubble Column Bioreactor; EC, Elimination Capacity;
404 TSS, Total Suspended Solids; TOC, Total organic Carbon, IC, Inorganic Carbon thin layer
405 chromatography.

406 **Electronic Annex.** Table A.1, Figure A₁, Figure A₂.

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412

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569 **7. Figure captions**

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571 **Figure 1.** Diagram of the experimental set-up. (1) Bubble column bioreactor, (2) mixing
572 chamber, (3) rotameter, (4) mass flow controller, (5) peristaltic pump, (6) cooling water, (7)
573 condenser, (8) liquid sampling port, (9) gas sampling port.

574

575 **Figure 2.** Time course of CH₄ (■), CO₂ (▲) and TSS (●) concentration during the cultivation
576 of the pure strain *M. alcaliphilum* 20Z (left) and the enriched haloalkaliphilic methanotrophic
577 consortium (right) using CH₄, H₂S-free biogas and biogas as carbon and energy source. The
578 error bars represent the standard deviation between duplicates.

579

580 **Figure 3.** Final intra-cellular ectoine yield (A) and growth rate (B) inoculated with *M.*
581 *alcaliphilum* (black columns) or the haloalkaliphilic consortium (grey columns) during the
582 batch biogas bioconversion experiments (TS1-6). Vertical lines represent standard deviations
583 from duplicate measurements. Paired columns with different letters were significantly different
584 at p<0.05.

585

586 **Figure 4.** Steady state intra-cellular ectoine yields, elimination capacities (EC) and biomass
587 concentration during the continuous biogas bioconversion experiments in BCB in S1 (white
588 column), S2 (grey column), S3 (spotted column), S4 (black column), S5 (squared column) and
589 S6 (striped column). Vertical lines represent standard deviations from steady state
590 measurements.

591

592 **Figure 5.** Heatmap showing the differential relative abundance of the most significant 53
593 OTUs (represented as 12 bacterial orders) under steady state in stages 3, 4, 5 and 6 during BCB
594 operation. OTUs with relative abundances < 0.5 were not included in the data analysis.

Table 1. Experimental conditions during the continuous biogas bioconversion into ectoine.

Operational Stage	Inoculum (description)	Headspace gas composition (%)	Gas recycling (L min ⁻¹)	EBRT (min)	Virtual EBRT (min)	Medium exchange (L d ⁻¹)	Inlet CH ₄ load (g m ⁻³ h ⁻¹)
S1	<i>M. alcaliphilum</i> 20Z	CH ₄ :O ₂ :CO ₂ 35:55.0:10	1	33.3	2	0.1	342 ± 45.8
S2	<i>M. alcaliphilum</i> 20Z	CH ₄ :O ₂ :CO ₂ 35:55.0:10	0	33.3	33.3	0.1	342 ± 45.8
S3	Haloalkaliphilic consortium	CH ₄ :O ₂ :CO ₂ 35:55.0:10	1	33.3	2	0.1	340 ± 33.2
S4	Haloalkaliphilic consortium	CH ₄ :O ₂ :CO ₂ 35:55.0:10	0	33.3	33.3	0.1	322 ± 19.9
S5	Haloalkaliphilic consortium	CH ₄ :O ₂ :He 35:55.0:10	1	33.3	2	0.1	488 ± 85.6
S6	Haloalkaliphilic consortium	CH ₄ :O ₂ :He 35:55.0:10	1	33.3	2	1	380 ± 37.0

596 9. Figures

597 Figure 1.

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632 Figure 5.

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